

Early V&V in Knowledge-Centric Systems Engineering: Advances and Benefits in Practice

Jose Luis de la Vara
Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha, Spain
jose.luis.delavara@uclm.es

Juan Manuel Morote
Independent Researcher, Spain

Clara Ayora
Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha, Spain
clara.ayora@uclm.es

Giovanni Giachetti
Universitat Politècnica de València, Spain
Universidad Andrés Bello, Chile
giovanni.giachetti@unab.cl

Luis Alonso
The REUSE Company, Spain
luis.alonso@reusecompany.com

Roy Mendieta
The REUSE Company, Spain
roy.mendieta@reusecompany.com

David Muñoz
The REUSE Company, Spain
david.munoz@reusecompany.com

Ricardo Ruiz-Nolasco
RGB Medical Devices, Spain
ruiznolasco@rgb-medical.com

Antonio González
RGB Medical Devices, Spain
agonzalez@rgb-medical.com

Abstract—Knowledge-Centric Systems Engineering is an industrial approach to systems and software engineering that advocates the development and use of knowledge bases that represent system domains. This approach can also exploit artificial intelligence techniques. These means can be used for early V&V (verification and validation) activities, e.g., for system artefact quality analysis and traceability management. This paper presents advances made in these activities with the SES Engineering Studio industrial tool and its underlying methods to meet further early-V&V needs in practice. The methods and the tool have been improved to better address model quality analysis, traceability project management, trace specification, and compliance with standards. For validation, we have initially applied the new features on a medical device. This has also allowed us to study the benefits of the features. The results show that the advances made can lead to wider system artefact analyses, more precise traceability management, better system artefacts, lower V&V effort, and lower issue resolution costs. All in all, the paper presents specific examples of how early-V&V industrial practices and tools can be improved.

Keywords—*Knowledge-Centric Systems Engineering, Early V&V, Quality analysis, Traceability, SES Engineering Studio.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The engineering of large and complex software-intensive systems is usually a challenging activity that requires the execution of different lifecycle processes to ensure system dependability [15]. Various systems engineering approaches exist with different principles on how to best address these processes. An example is Knowledge-Centric Systems Engineering (KCSE) [32], an industrial approach whose adoption is growing. It can be regarded as a specialisation of model-based systems engineering that advocates that all lifecycle processes are affected by the existence of knowledge bases about a system. Such knowledge bases can be created by means of ontologies that represent system domains and consider different types of knowledge elements and of semantic aspects. Artificial intelligence (AI) techniques can also use the bases for,

e.g., Natural Language Processing (NLP) and expert system features that enable and support KCSE [48].

The ontologies managed in KCSE can be exploited for different systems engineering purposes [48]. This includes V&V (verification & validation) at early system development stages, such as the requirements engineering and architectural design phases. It is at these stages when decisions are made about what a system will support and how. It is necessary that such decisions and their corresponding representation in specifications are adequate, e.g., requirements must be right and satisfied in a system's architecture.

We are particularly interested in two activities for early V&V. First, system artefact quality analysis [39] aims to confirm that artefacts such as risks analyses, requirements, and architectural specifications are correct, consistent, and complete. Second, traceability management [8] deals with the specification, analysis, and maintenance of relationships between system artefacts, e.g., between requirements and architectural elements, to confirm the alignment between different system artefacts and lifecycle processes. Furthermore, system artefact quality analysis and traceability management are required by standards [36] such as DO-178C [43] in aerospace, ISO 26262 [27] in automotive, and IEC 62304 [24] in healthcare, as their results contribute to developing confidence in system dependability. The activities can exploit the knowledge specified in an ontology about, e.g., system concepts, their relationships, and a system's structure. The selection of the activities was based on needs and potential benefits in industry.

In this context, we present recent advances in early V&V in KCSE with SES Engineering Studio [48] (hereafter referred to as SES), an industrial tool. The overall goal has been to meet further early-V&V needs in practice. We report on how SES methods and capabilities for system artefact quality analysis and for traceability management have been improved. The work has been conducted mostly in the scope of VALU3S [2], a large-scale industry-academia project. V&V methods and tools were reviewed [49], gaps and limitations were analysed [50],

improvements were suggested [51] and realised [53], and usage workflows were specified [52]. The gaps and limitations to deal with were selected according to industrial challenges, expectations, priorities, and added value. For quality analysis, the improvements have focused on extended model analysis; for traceability, on enhanced management process. Link with compliance needs is also an improvement area for both activities. The work on these areas addresses industrial needs.

The resulting methods and tool support have been validated with a NMT (neuromuscular transmission) controller [55], as a specific real, practical scenario. It is a medical device for muscle relaxation measurement that aims at simplifying the protocol to be followed by anaesthetists. The benefits on early V&V have also been studied. This is important because of the little evidence of the advantages of advanced early-V&V means in KCSE, as concluded in the analysis of gaps and limitations in VALU3S.

The main contribution of the paper is to show how early V&V in KCSE in practice has been improved, how the improvements can be applied, and their benefits. This includes AI features, although they are not the main focus of this paper. The contribution is useful for researchers and practitioners working on or using KCSE, as well as others interested in new results for early V&V or KCSE. Overall, the paper reports on the specific application of certain industrial features and on their advantages, taking impact and practicality into account. It is a concrete example of how V&V KCSE practices and tools can be assessed and improved in real-world environments, and of advances and benefits in which industry is interested. Furthermore, the improvement areas addressed are relevant not only to KCSE and SES, but also to other solutions. For instance, the insights from the analyses conducted and the tool features defined are applicable to other industrial means for quality analysis and traceability management, e.g., [6][9][28][33].

The rest of the paper is organised as follows. Section 2 presents its background. Section 3 describes the advances in early V&V, and Section 4 their validation with the NMT controller. Finally, Section 5 summarises our conclusions.

II. BACKGROUND

This section introduces SES and reviews related work.

A. SES Engineering Studio

SES [48] is a commercial KCSE environment developed by The REUSE Company (TRC) to support and coordinate systems and software engineering processes. It is used by large companies, e.g., Airbus, Ariane, and Toyota, among others. SES enables integration with many existing tools, such as tools for requirements management (DOORS, Polarion, Teamcenter...) and for model-based systems engineering (Enterprise Architect, MagicDraw, Rhapsody...).

SES includes several (sub-)tools that support different key KCSE activities:

- RQA - Quality Studio (hereafter referred to as RQA) for quality analysis. It allows users to define, calculate, manage, and report quality of systems artefacts based on best practices, and to identify possible issues and defects. For instance, RQA can analyse requirements correctness, consistency, and completeness in line with

the INCOSE Guide to Writing Requirements [25] or company-specific recommendations.

- V&V Studio for general quality management. It manages V&V actions for quality assessment processes, including manual actions, e.g., via checklists. This enables V&V for a broad variety of needs and artefacts.
- Traceability Studio for traceability management. It provides support to specify and manage relationships between system artefacts, including change impact analysis.
- Knowledge Manager for ontology development. It supports the creation and maintenance of knowledge bases, e.g., about a system, its requirements, and its design models.

All in all, SES can be regarded as an expert, rule-based system for systems and software engineering that exploits semantic information about a domain and that uses AI techniques such as NLP and machine learning.

As input, SES can import data from external tools and system artefacts. They include SysML, UML and simulation models, MS Excel spreadsheets, MS Word documents, and requirements from different repositories and in different formats.

SES exploits ontologies with five distinct parts (Fig. 1):

- Vocabulary, which includes the terms used in a specific domain and their syntactic information; e.g., the word 'car' is a noun.
- Conceptual Model, which focuses on semantics and relationships, including system architectures and relationship types; e.g., the semantics of 'car' can be 'system', it specializes 'vehicle', and it has an 'engine'.
- Patterns, which are templates (aka boilerplates) used for structured system information specification; e.g., for textual requirements.
- Formalization, which involves the semantic representation of system information according to patterns and rules; e.g., for system artefact data import and later analysis.
- Reasoning, with procedures to infer information; e.g., about specification correctness based on the content, structure, and semantics of textual requirements and of model elements.

B. Related Work

V&V in general and early V&V in particular are areas that have received attention in the scope of KCSE, both with SES and with other solutions.

As a result of the growing interest in ontology-based systems and software engineering, it has become easier to find publications on this topic. The use of ontologies has been proposed to support, e.g., safety, security, and dependability risk assessment [3], requirements verification [7], security V&V [45], and testing [29]. Some publications have dealt with both ontologies and models, e.g., for V&V process definition [10] and for reliability and safety analysis [58], or with both ontologies and AI, e.g., for requirements analysis [57] and for test case generation [30]. Prior work has also proposed traceability approaches that exploit ontologies, e.g., [23][35].

Fig. 1. Example of structure of a SES ontology [47]

Nonetheless, the structure and content of the ontologies used in these publications are different to those exploited by SES, which consist of further element types, are based on industrial needs and practices, and enable more detailed and broader early V&V.

When analysing existing tools for system artefact quality analysis such as Ansys medini analyze [6], MXAM [33], and QVscribe [40], it could be argued that they exploit knowledge about a system. Taking the parts of SES ontologies as a reference, these tools consider, e.g., system structure aspects, formalise system artefact data when importing it, and reason from this data. The same applies to traceability management tools such as itemis ANALYZE [28], Reqtify [9], and Visure [56]. However, these tools are less flexible than SES and provide a more limited support for KCSE, mainly because they do not focus on ontology development as a key engineering task. SES allows system engineers to configure and customise ontologies and tool features in more detail according to system- and project-specific characteristics. Other tools do not allow users to declare their own ontology elements for all the areas of a SES ontology and exploit little specific semantic information in their analyses. This results in narrower early V&V.

Prior publications on early V&V with SES have most often dealt with requirements quality analysis, e.g., [20][21]. They have considered the use of advanced AI features based on techniques such as genetic algorithms [1] and machine learning [37]. We presented recently how to combine Arcadia/Capella and SES for model-based reliability-oriented system design [25], exploiting their existing integration and means. We extend these results in this paper by presenting advances in artefact quality analysis and traceability management not reported yet.

In the scope of the AMASS project [14], we made progress with SES in different early V&V-related areas. For assurance and certification purposes, RQA was integrated with a method and tool for assurance evidence management [17] and was used for safety case analysis [12]. Artefact quality analysis [39] was enhanced through new requirements and model analysis metrics and through support for checklist definition and usage. The integration with other tools [13][16] enabled new model quality

analyses and traceability management actions. We also worked on the analysis of requirements quality evolution [38], ontology development in the context of compliance with safety standards [11], and ontology configuration management [31]. Other areas to which we have contributed include trace discovery [5], tool interoperability [4], compliance assessment [22], and ontology-based analysis of the text of safety standards [18]. The advances presented in this paper build on many of these prior results, extending and enhancing them towards better early V&V in industry through new SES features.

In summary, results on early V&V in KCSE have been presented in other publications and it could be argued that other tools support it. The contribution of this paper is to report on the latest advances made for system artefact quality analysis and traceability management with SES, as well as on their application on a specific system. In addition, several aspects addressed for SES in this paper have not received, in our opinion, sufficient attention in prior work, especially from an industrial perspective. Relevant aspects that have not been addressed in depth include Capella diagram quality analysis beyond the limited support that the Capella tool provides, advanced configuration and semantics-based exploitation of traceability information, and alignment of ontology-based system artefact quality analyses and traceability management with requirements from assurance standards.

III. ADVANCES IN EARLY V&V

This section describes the advances made in early V&V in KCSE for system artefact quality analysis and for traceability management. Due to page limitations, we provide a broad view of the advances. In addition, many implementation details cannot be provided for confidentiality reasons. They are part of the knowledge and intellectual property of TRC.

A. System Artefact Quality Analysis

The suitability of system artefacts in different formats can be assessed with RQA by exploiting ontologies, semantic information, and AI. From metrics and measurement procedures based on best practices specified in the Reasoning part of an

ontology, RQA quantitatively assesses system artefact quality and assigns a quality level (high, medium, low; see Fig. 2). For instance, RQA can determine if a given requirement contains suitable terms or correctly follows some pattern. This also requires the application of NLP. In addition, V&V Studio supports manual quality assessment by allowing users to define and execute their own V&V actions, e.g., via checklists. The outcome can be integrated with RQA automatic analyses for a global quality view.

The practical gaps and limitations identified in system artefact quality analysis with SES [50] included that the amount of model-specific quality analysis means was limited, as most of the available support focused on textual requirements. In addition, no explicit and direct link with compliance had been established for most assurance and engineering standards, and little empirical evidence of cost-effectiveness was available. The improvements enabled can be summarised as follows.

Extended model quality analysis. The improvements in this area have strongly focused on the definition of means for quality analysis when using the Arcadia method [42] and the Capella tool [19] for model-based system engineering. The method and tool support requirements analysis and design for systems, hardware, and software, considering different views. Integration of SES with, e.g., Cameo Systems Modeler and MS Office has also been enhanced, resulting in an extension of the Formalization part of the ontologies. The improvements have considered:

- The mapping between Capella diagrams and the (semantic) data schema used by SES for system artefact quality analysis. This way, information can be extracted from Capella diagrams and stored in a semantic representation, linking the information with other ontology elements.
- How the diagrams can be extended for detailed quality analysis, e.g., through the Capella viewpoint extension mechanism. This allows a user to include further information in Capella diagrams about aspects such as system component reliability.
- The existing means for quality analysis that can be used off the shelf on Capella diagrams, mainly based on NLP. For instance, the text of the elements of a diagram can be analysed regarding text precision, ambiguity, and consistency.
- New means for quality analysis that could be used, including wizards for quality metric definition and configuration from the element types and structures of, e.g., a Capella project (Fig. 3). More concretely, new ways to analyse model quality have been enabled. It is now possible to, e.g., count the number of elements in a Capella diagram with a certain characteristic or related to elements in other diagrams. SES Reasoning support has been extended to enable this improvement.
- How the development of Capella diagrams can benefit from on-the-fly quality analyses and how they could be enabled, e.g., via a Capella add-on. This extension

Fig. 2. Quality analysis with RQA

mechanism is used for integration of Capella with commercial tools. For instance, SES makes it possible to add textual requirements in Capella diagrams, to do it according to patterns, and to know how good the requirements are while writing them.

These improvements are relevant for anyone and for any tool interested in model quality analysis in general and in Capella diagram quality analysis in particular. They could be adapted and implemented for other tools. The extension and customization opportunities that wizard-based quality metric definition offers are especially valuable for flexible system artefact quality analysis in practice.

Fig. 3. Metrics for model element types in RQA

Link with compliance needs. A process has been defined to systematically represent information and compliance needs from standards in ontologies and to later exploit such information to follow a standard and assess compliance, e.g., for DO-178C in aerospace, ISO 26262 in automotive, and IEC 62304 in healthcare. Among its characteristics, the process considers:

- Inclusion of the terminology specific to a standard in an ontology (e.g., fault).
- Definition of semantic information for aspects such as the concepts of a standard (e.g., software element concepts), the types of possible relationships between system artefacts (e.g., for the fact that a test case validates some requirements), and the relationship between general concepts and standard-specific ones (e.g., between requirement and high-level requirement).
- Provision of textual patterns in accordance with a standard's terminology and semantics, e.g., to specify that a requirement refers to a software element.
- Mapping of general quality analysis metrics to the concrete compliance needs of a standard, e.g., for requirements consistency assessment.
- Development of checklists for compliance assessment, e.g., to indicate whether it is judged that high-level requirements comply with system requirements.

Although defined in the scope of early V&V in KCSE, this process is relevant for any compliance management approach. Among the improvements, the mapping of quality analysis metrics and its use can make compliance assessment and demonstration in industry more efficient.

The improvement on system artefact quality analysis has resulted in compliance-aware extended knowledge-centric system artefact quality analysis. Its purpose is to quantitatively determine the suitability of system artefacts in different formats

by exploiting ontologies, semantic information, and AI, according to selected criteria (e.g., correctness, consistency, and completeness) and considering specific compliance needs from assurance standards.

- The input is: System artefacts to analyse, Ontology to exploit for the analysis, Configuration of metrics for quantitative quality assessment, Assurance standards.
- The intermediate result is: Representation of information of assurance standards in the ontology.
- The output is: Quality analysis reports.

The new, revised general workflow is as follows:

1. *Define metrics*: Specification, if needed, of the characteristics of new metrics (measurement procedure, quality levels...) to use for system artefact quality analysis.
2. *Select metrics*: Determination of the set of metrics to use for a given quality analysis, considering the requirements from applicable assurance standards.
3. *Define system artefacts import mechanism*: Determination of the means to import, from other tools, artefact data for quality analysis purposes, and of how the means will be used.
4. *Run quality analysis*: Execution of a system artefact quality analysis according to a given metrics configuration and to the content of a given ontology, resulting in a quality analysis report.
5. *Update system artefacts*: Revision of system artefacts in case quality issues are identified, to address the issues.

B. Traceability Management

Relationships between system artefacts can be managed with Traceability Studio (Fig. 4), which can further exploit ontologies to this end. The tool enables system engineers to manage various system artefact types through SES connectivity features that retrieve traceability information from other sources. This exploits the Formalization part of an ontology, which in turn can use NLP. Traceability projects contain modules with a source and a target, and traces between the system artefacts can be specified and later used for, e.g., V&V purposes or change impact analysis. The ontologies support the reuse of relationship types (Conceptual model part) and enable semantic comparison for actions such as trace discovery and verification. This comparison is based on inference procedures of the Reasoning part of an ontology.

The practical gaps and limitations identified in traceability management with SES [50] included that several activities of the management process [8] were not supported. In addition, and as system artefact quality analysis, no explicit and direct link with compliance had been established for most assurance standards, and little empirical evidence of cost-effectiveness was available. The improvements on traceability management enabled can be summarised as follows.

Enhanced traceability management process. The process for traceability management has been refined and extended to better support traceability activities. The main improvements can be summarised as follows:

- Definition of maps for the projects (Fig. 5), to show an overview of the configuration, modules, and data

Fig. 4. Traceability information in Traceability Studio

sources of a project. Maps have also been associated to the individual modules of a traceability project.

- Semantic configuration, to specify aspects such as trace types and basic trace information retrieval configuration based on the semantics of relationships or of traced elements. This can be aligned with the trace types and artefact types to manage for compliance with assurance standards.
- Advanced trace information retrieval configuration, currently used to suggest traces and identify suspect ones (i.e., traces to check). The possible configurations affect similarity thresholds, NLP configuration for retrieval, and the retrieval method (inclusion or similarity). For instance, a user can specify a similarity threshold for discovery, i.e., how semantically similar two system artefacts must be so that SES determines that there may be a relationship between them.
- As follow-up improvements, traces can be discovered (suggested ones) and evaluated (suspect ones). A semantic distance score is provided. The traces are then classified as Suspect, Suggested, and Consistent. For instance, the small labels of the links in Fig. 5 indicate the total number of traces between the artefacts and the number of consistent, suspect, and suggested traces.
- Configuration of trace discovery and evaluation according to additional semantic information. This way, the semantic information of specification patterns and clusters (system semantic categories) is also considered.
- Trace history management, to keep track of trace lifecycle, such as when a trace was created or suggested, or when a suspect one was reviewed.
- Graph generation for impact analysis, with different visualisation options, such as a general project-wide graph at system artefact source level, a graph with only the elements of a module, grouping of graph elements according to some common property (e.g., artefact format), and tree-like (or hierarchical) views.
- Further mapping of the underlying data model to those of other tools (e.g., DOORS and Capella) for traceability data exchange, in turn enabling further relationship specification and analysis possibilities because of the exploitation of more data.
- New report generation possibilities and in different formats, according to the information managed about a traceability project.
- Use (and reuse) of traceability information in ontologies of standards, e.g., about trace types and traced element

types specified in the Conceptual model part of an ontology, to enable alignment with the standards.

These improvements are relevant for anyone and any tool dealing with traceability management. The new features represent novel ways towards better industrial practices for, e.g., traceability project configuration and analysis, trace discovery, and trace evaluation, by exploiting semantic information.

The improvement on traceability management has resulted in extended knowledge-centric system traceability management. Its purpose is to manage the relationships between system artefact by taking advantage of ontologies, semantic information and AI, further supporting advanced traceability project configuration and automating trace discovery and verification.

- The input is: System artefacts to trace, Ontology to exploit for traceability purposes.
- The intermediate result is: Traceability project map, Ontology configuration, Initial traces between system artefacts (subject to review), Suggested and suspect traces, Change impact analysis information.
- The output is: Traces between system artefacts, Ontology updated with traceability information, Traceability graphs, Trace history, Traceability reports.

The new, revised general workflow is as follows:

1. *Define relationship types*: Characterization, if needed, of (new) types of relationships between system artefacts to consider for a given traceability management effort.
2. *Define traceability project map*: Specification of how a project will be, considering aspects such as the system artefact sources from other tools to consider and the parameters for traceability tasks (trace discovery, specification, verification...).
3. *Trace system artefacts*: Specification of relationships between system artefacts.
4. *Discover traces*: Automatic proposal of possible relationships between system artefacts.
5. *Review traces*: Trace check to confirm that the traces specified are valid.
6. *Analyse artefact change impact*: Determination of the effect that system artefact changes have or might have.

IV. VALIDATION OF THE ADVANCES

This section describes how the advances made in early V&V in KCSE have been applied on the NMT controller for initial validation purposes. Such an application corresponds to one of the industrial demonstrators of the VALU3S project [54]. It is a real, practical scenario that has allowed us to use the advances with real-world, industrial data. In line with case study research [44], we aimed to investigate contemporary phenomena within their real-life context in an exploratory and flexible way.

The goal was to evaluate the advances made in early V&V in KCSE. We formulated two research questions:

- RQ1: Are the advances a feasible means for early V&V in KCSE?
- RQ2: What benefits can the use of the advances in early V&V in KCSE lead to?

The goal and the RQs are aligned with and are similar to those in prior publications, e.g., [16][17].

Fig. 5. Traceability module map in Traceability Studio

The next sections present the design, the results, and a discussion of the application of the advances.

A. Design

The advances in early V&V in KCSE were applied on an NMT controller [55] developed by RGB Medical Devices [41]. It is an intelligent infusion controller for muscle relaxation that monitors specific vital signs to be regulated. It also infuses, at regular intervals, an updated drug dose value to achieve a specific target value for the physiological sign under control. This device aims to use a very innovative technology to support the anaesthesiologist during an operating room intervention.

RGB engineers developed the NMT controller and provided data about it, TRC engineers implemented the advances in early V&V in SES, and the second author was the main responsible for applying the advances, including their AI features. The rest of authors supported him when needed. The advances were applied with the following data:

- *Risk analysis report*: Fifty-six entries with types of hazards, causes, effects, and actions (to address the risks) were available in a Word document. For instance, the risk analysis referred to wrong dose infusion or incorrect determination of the systolic, diastolic, and mean blood pressures. The sets of individual types of hazards (21), causes (51), effects (46), and actions (84) were stored in Excel spreadsheets.
- *System requirements*: Forty-two textual system requirements were extracted from the risk analysis report and stored in an Excel spreadsheet. There were 41 safety requirements and one security requirement.

For instance, the requirements referred to system alarms, such as “When the autonomy is reduced, an alarm message is activated by software”.

- *System models:* Seven Capella diagrams were created from available system information; one Operational Capabilities diagram, one System Architecture diagram, one Model State Machine diagram, one Logical Component Breakdown diagram, and three Logical Architecture diagrams. For instance, the models represented (1) that a user can check the dose calculated by the control algorithm of the NMT controller and can pause or adjust the drug infusion, and (2) the functions, components, and component relationships of the sensor, controller, and infusion pump of the medical device. Fig. 6 shows a model of the NMT controller. It includes functions that a user and the system can perform, such as ‘Check dose’ and ‘Calculate optimal dose’, respectively.
- *Applicable standards:* IEC 62304 (Medical device software) and ISO 14971 (Application of risk management to medical devices) [26] were considered.

SES had not been used at RGB before the validation. RGB engineers analysed manually, on Word documents, the quality of risk analysis data and of system requirements. They managed traceability with the same tool support, with limited automation for change impact analysis (functionality for search in a document). RGB engineers did not employ AI support (rule- and semantics-based support, NLP, etc.) for V&V in the past.

For the study of the benefits, we used criteria defined and agreed upon by the VALU3S consortium (41 partners, including 25 industrial partners from seven different application domains). The criteria cover requirements satisfaction, system issue detection, joint management of safety and security requirements, and cost and time for work on functional safety and certification activities [46]. Some metrics can be used to study several evaluation areas.

Fig. 6. System functions of the NMT controller (selection)

B. Results

We analysed the quality of risk analysis elements, system requirements, and system models with RQA and V&V Studio (example in Fig. 2). With Traceability Studio, traceability management dealt with the traces in the risk analysis report (428) and traces between system requirements and Capella diagrams (examples in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5). We used Knowledge Manager for both early-V&V activities. We represented information from IEC 62304 and ISO 14971 in ontologies (Fig. 7) and created compliance checklists with V&V Studio. For instance, a checklist of IEC 62304 referred to the expected content of the software requirements specification. We executed all the activities of the general workflows for system artefact quality analysis and for traceability management and applied all the improvements to some extent.

Fig. 7. Relationship types of IEC 62304 in Knowledge Manager

When estimating certain gains from SES usage outcome, e.g., about effort and cost reductions, RGB engineers used past average projects as a reference. Detailed data from prior projects was not available for a precise comparison, but the engineers were experienced and considered that they could provide representative, valid approximate values. In other words, RGB engineers indicated, based on their experience and knowledge, the extent to which they thought that effort and cost could be reduced thanks to the advances applied on the NMT controller. For cost reduction in issue resolution, RGB engineers considered past situations in which the issues were identified at later lifecycle stages, during reviews by external assessors as a part of, e.g., the certification process of the medical devices developed by the company.

The main results for **system artefact quality analysis** can be summarised as follows, per evaluation area.

Requirements satisfaction: Support for the detection and resolution of safety- or security-related requirements issues in the system artefacts considered.

- 38 new automatic quality analyses enabled (e.g., about text precision) for the different system artefacts
- Use of six compliance checklists (one for IEC 62304 and five for ISO 14971) on the different system artefacts
- Improvement on system requirements specification, reducing the ratio of low-quality requirements from 31% (13 system requirements) to 12% (five) only following base RQA recommendations (based on industrial best practices; e.g., to avoid imprecise terms)

System issue detection: Support for the resolution of issues in safety requirements.

- Improvement of 41 safety requirements thanks to RQA recommendations

Joint management of safety and security requirements: Support for the analysis and resolution of safety- or security-related requirements issues.

- Joint improvement of 42 safety or security requirements
- Use of six compliance checklists (one for IEC 62304 and five for IEC 14971) for safety- or security-related requirements aspects

Cost and time for work on functional safety and certification activities: Estimation, by RGB engineers, of effort and cost reductions thanks to automated system artefact quality analysis for the system artefacts considered (required by standards, e.g., as a verification activity; average project as a reference).

- At least 20% effort reduction in system artefact quality analysis for the different system artefacts as a whole
- At least 25% cost reduction in system artefact issue resolution thanks to early (instead of late) issue detection, for the different system artefacts as a whole

For **traceability management**, these are the main results.

Requirements satisfaction: Support for trace discovery and change impact analysis for the system artefacts considered.

- Automatic trace discovery for a set of 44 valid traces (70% precision) between Capella diagrams and system requirements, with the default discovery configuration of Traceability Studio (same for other discovery results)
- Tool-supported identification of 330 potential change impacts on risk analysis information affecting several trace chains

System issue detection: Support for the discovery of safety requirement traces and of traces whose disregard could lead to issues or whose identification confirms that possible issues have been addressed.

- Automatic trace discovery for 49% of safety requirements
- Automatic impact analysis for 428 risk analysis traces

Joint management of safety and security requirements: Support for trace discovery and change impact analysis, considering both safety and security requirements, and the rest of system artefacts.

- Joint automatic trace discovery of a set of 44 valid traces (70% precision) between Capella diagrams and safety or security requirements
- Joint automatic impact analysis for a set of 428 risk analysis traces (including security aspects)

- Joint tool-supported identification of 330 potential change impacts on risk analysis information (including security aspects) affecting several trace chains

Cost and time for work on functional safety and certification activities: Estimation, by RGB engineers, of effort and cost reductions thanks to automated traceability management for the system artefacts considered (required by standards, e.g., trace specification and change impact analysis; average project as a reference).

- At least 40% effort reduction in change impact analysis for the different system artefacts as a whole
- At least 25% cost reduction in traceability issue resolution thanks to early (instead of late) issue detection, for the different system artefacts as a whole

Finally, certain specific details of the results cannot be provided for confidentiality reasons, e.g., about how the risks of the NMT controller were addressed, the set of specific system requirements improved, or the NMT controller design information represented in Capella diagrams. This information is part of the knowledge and intellectual property of RGB.

C. Discussion

This section discusses the answers to the RQs formulated and the validity of the application of the advances.

We argue that the advances applied on the NMT controller are a feasible means for early V&V in KCSE (**RQ1**). We could successfully perform system artefact quality analysis and traceability management with RQA and Traceability Studio, respectively, considering risk analysis data, system requirements, system models, and applicable standards of the NMT controller. We also used V&V Studio and Knowledge Manager. We dealt with different system artefact types and in different formats.

The results also allow us to conclude that the use of the advances in early V&V in KCSE can lead to benefits (**RQ2**). Such benefits were identified and quantitatively assessed for both system artefact quality analysis and traceability management. Most notably, the percentage of low-quality system requirements was reduced by following the base recommendations that RQA provides (developed and used by industrial experts), automatic trace discovery with the default mechanisms of Traceability Studio resulted in trace discovery for around half the system requirements, the joint improvement of safety and security requirements was enabled, and effort for change impact analysis was reduced by 40% (estimation by RGB engineers; past average projects as a reference).

All in all, the outcome of the demonstrator led to:

- Wider system artefact quality analysis, thanks to the new analyses enabled for different artefact types, including checklist-based analyses.
- More precise traceability management, thanks to the new support for trace discovery, trace review, and change impact analysis in and between various engineering phases.
- Better system artefacts, thanks to the resolution of the quality issues detected.

- Lower effort in the addressed V&V tasks, thanks to the automated support for early V&V.
- Lower cost in issue resolution, thanks to the earlier detection of system artefact quality issues and of traceability-related issues.

When considering the **validity** of the application and its results, certain threats exist. We have been involved in the application of the advances. The results might be different for others that, e.g., have not contributed to the development of the advances or are less experienced with SES. Having applied the advances only in one case makes it difficult to ensure that the results and the benefits, and their extent, will be the same in other contexts, including those in which SES is already used.

On the other hand, validity is positively impacted from facts such as the effective use of SES in different companies and application domains (automotive, aviation, defence, energy, healthcare, railway, space...) and for different systems, and its maturity. The past successful performance of SES for large, complex systems regarding, e.g., scalability and reliability makes us confident in the quality of the features developed and of their integration with other features. Dealing with risk analysis, requirements, and architectural specifications, and in different formats, is also a representative scenario of early-V&V needs in industry. In addition, the new SES features have been identified, selected and developed in a generic way. They can be used for other systems. As argued in more detail in Section III, the features are also relevant to and could be adopted in other early-V&V methods and tools, including industrial ones, both because of their generalizability and because of their added value for practitioners.

Regarding other application and validity aspects, the use of the methods and tools requires an initial effort for configuration, such as the development of ontologies, the selection of quality aspects to analyse, or the selection of specific tool behaviours among different alternatives (e.g., for trace discovery). This has been considered when estimating effort and cost reductions. It is also important to note that RGB is an SME whose staff are highly specialised in and knowledgeable about the systems that they develop and how to address system artefact quality, traceability, and compliance for them. Their experience helps them perform the underlying activities effectively and efficiently. The estimated gains will arguably be greater in companies developing a wider range of systems or larger systems, or where the staff are less experienced. Finally, although relevant for critical domains, tool qualification aspects are out of the scope of the work presented in this paper.

V. CONCLUSION

As the engineering of large and complex software-intensive systems becomes more challenging, the use of advanced approaches such as KCSE becomes more necessary to succeed. The approaches also need to evolve and progress to provide new means that make systems engineering activities more cost-effective in practice, including early-V&V activities.

We have presented the latest advances for early V&V in KCSE regarding system artefact quality analysis and traceability management with SES. Quality analysis has been improved via extended model quality analysis and link with compliance

needs, new features such as quality analyses for Capella diagrams, and ontology development with knowledge from standards. For traceability management, the main improvements have resulted in an enhanced traceability management process, e.g., via traceability project maps and advanced trace discovery and verification. These are practical solutions that exploit AI and are already impacting early V&V in industry.

We have applied the advances with system artefacts of a NMT controller, as a real, practical scenario. We have considered information about risks analysis, system requirements, system models, and applicable standards for system artefact quality analysis and traceability management purposes. The advances enabled new system artefact quality analyses, quality issue identification and resolution, automatic and automated traceability tasks, and (estimated) effort and cost reductions. We argue that, overall, the advances in early V&V presented can lead to wider system artefact analyses, more precise traceability management, better system artefacts, lower V&V effort, and lower issue resolution cost. These are important benefits for any company that develops critical systems, for which quality assurance and V&V are musts and their effort and costs are high.

We consider that the work reported is a valuable example of new advanced features early V&V in practice, their application, and their potential benefits, illustrating different early-V&V aspects in which industry is interested. The advances presented are relevant to other approaches and tools, as they correspond to features for system artefact quality analysis and for traceability management that can be valuable in industry and from which practitioners can benefit. It is also important for academia to know what aspects of system artefact quality analysis and of traceability management are currently being addressed in practice. The work further contributes to filling the gaps about the little empirical evidence of the cost-effectiveness of KCSE in general and of SES solutions in particular, including their AI-based features.

As future work, we plan to continue studying the application of the advances with other systems, including with SES users and their KCSE projects, and covering different application domains. We will also continue to work on new solutions for quality analysis and traceability management of system artefacts. For instance, we are working on the definition and implementation of new, specific quality metrics for Capella diagrams. We are also interested in new traceability features such as more detailed project-wide trace verification and change impact analysis.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The work leading to this paper has received funding from the VALU3S (H2020-ECSEL ref. 876852; MCIN/AEI ref. PCI2020-112001; NextGen.EU/PRTR), REBECCA (HORIZON-KDT ref. 101097224; MCIN/AEI ref. PCI2022-135043-2; NextGen.EU/PRTR), AETERNAL (MCIN/AEI ref. PID2023-149753OB-C21; ERDF), Music360 (HORIZON 101094872), and “Paradigmas de interacción para la nueva era de resiliencia digital” (UCLM ref. 2022-GRIN-34436; ERDF) projects, from the TASOVA PLUS research network (MCIN/AEI ref. RED2022-134337-T), and from the Ramon y Cajal Program (MCIN/AEI ref. RYC-2017-22836; ESF).

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Adanza, V. Moreno, G. Génova, "An automatic methodology for the quality enhancement of requirements using genetic algorithms," *Information and Software Technology*, vol. 140, 106696, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.infsof.2021.106696
- [2] J.A. Agirre, Joseba Andoni Agirre, L. Etxeberria, R. Barbosa, S. Basagiannis, G. Giantamidis, T. Bauer, E. Ferrari, M. Labayen, V. Orani, J. Öberg, D. Pereira, J. Proença, R. Schlick, A. Smrcka, W. Tiberti, S. Tonetta, M. Bozzano, A. Yazici, B. Sangchoolie, "The VALU3S ECSEL project: Verification and validation of automated systems safety and security," *Microprocessors and Microsystems*, vol. 87, pp. 104349, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.micpro.2021.104349
- [3] J. Alanen, J. Linnosmaa, T. Malm, N. Papakonstantinou, T. Ahonen, E. Heikkilä, R. Tiusanen, "Hybrid ontology for safety, security, and dependability risk assessments and Security Threat Analysis (STA) method for industrial control systems," *Reliability Engineering & System Safety*, vol. 220, 108270, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.ress.2021.108270
- [4] J.M., Álvarez-Rodríguez, R. Mendieta, J.L. de la Vara, A. Fraga, J. Llorens, "Enabling system artefact exchange and selection through a Linked Data layer," *Journal of Universal Computer Science*, vol. 24(11), pp. 1536-1560, 2018, doi: 10.3217/jucs-024-11-1536
- [5] J.M. Álvarez-Rodríguez, R. Mendieta, V. Moreno, M. Sanchez-Puebal, J. Llorens, "Semantic recovery of traceability links between system artifacts," *International Journal of Software Engineering and Knowledge Engineering*, vol. 30(10), pp. 1415-1442, 2020, doi: 10.1142/S0218194020400197
- [6] Ansys, Ansys medini analyze (online) <https://www.ansys.com/products/safety-analysis/ansys-medini-analyze> (Accessed Oct 21, 2024)
- [7] R. Chen, C.H. Chen, Y. Liu, X. Ye, "Ontology-based requirement verification for complex systems," *Advanced Engineering Informatics*, vol. 46, pp. 101148, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.aei.2020.101148
- [8] J. Cleland-Huang, O. Gotel, A. Zisman (eds.): *Software and Systems Traceability*. Springer, 2012, doi: 10.1007/978-1-4471-2239-5
- [9] Dassault Systemes, Reqtify (online) <https://www.3ds.com/products/catia/reqtify> (Accessed Oct 21, 2024)
- [10] R. Delabeye, O. Penas, R. Plateaux, "Scalable ontology-based V&V process for heterogeneous systems and applications," 14th System Analysis and Modelling Conference (SAM 2022), doi: 10.1145/3550356.3561577
- [11] J.L. de la Vara, A. Gómez, E. Gallego, G. Génova, A. Fraga, "Representation of Safety Standards with Semantic Technologies Used in Industrial Environments," 6th International Workshop on Next Generation of System Assurance Approaches for Safety-Critical Systems (SASSUR 2017), doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-66284-8_22
- [12] J.L. de la Vara, G. Jimenez, R. Mendieta, E. Parra, "Assessment of the Quality of Safety Cases: A Research Preview," 25th International Working Conference Requirements Engineering: Foundation for Software Quality (REFSQ 2019), doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-15538-4_9
- [13] J.L. de la Vara, E. Parra, L. Alonso, R. Mendieta, B. López, J.M. Álvarez-Rodríguez, "Integration of Tool Support for Assurance and Certification and for Knowledge-Centric Systems Engineering," 9th IEEE International Workshop on Software Certification (WoSoCer 2019), doi: 10.1109/ISSREW.2019.00092
- [14] J.L. de la Vara, E. Parra, A. Ruiz, B. Gallina, "AMASS: A Large-Scale European Project to Improve the Assurance and Certification of Cyber-Physical Systems," 20th International Conference Product-Focused Software Process Improvement (PROFES 2019), doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-35333-9_49
- [15] J.L. de la Vara, T. Bauer, B. Fischer, M. Karaca, H. Madeira, M. Matschnig, S. Mazzini, G.S. Nandi, F. Patrone, D. Pereira, J. Proença, R. Schlick, S. Tonetta, U. Yayan, B. Sangchoolie, "A Proposal for the Classification of Methods for Verification and Validation of Safety, Cybersecurity, and Privacy of Automated Systems," 14th International Conf. on the Quality of Information and Communications Technology (QUATIC 2021), doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-85347-1_24
- [16] J.L. de la Vara, A. Ruiz, G. Blondelle, "Assurance and Certification of Cyber-Physical Systems: The AMASS Open Source Ecosystem," *Journal of Systems and Software*, vol. 171, 110812, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.jss.2020.110812
- [17] J.L. de la Vara, A. Garcia, J. Valero, C. Ayora, "Model-Based Assurance Evidence Management for Safety-Critical Systems," *Software and Systems Modeling*, vol. 21(6), pp. 2329-2365, 2022, doi: 10.1007/s10270-021-00957-z
- [18] J.L. de la Vara, H. Bahamonde, C. Ayora, "Assessment of the Quality of the Text of Safety Standards with Industrial Semantic Technologies," *Computer Standards & Interfaces*, vol. 88, 103803, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.csi.2023.103803
- [19] Eclipse, Capella (online) <https://mbse-capella.org/> (Accessed Oct 21, 2024)
- [20] E. Gallego, H.G. Chalé-Góngora, J. Llorens, J. Fuentes, J. Álvarez, G. Génova, A. Fraga, "Requirements Quality Analysis: A Successful Case Study in the Industry," 7th International Conference on Complex Systems Design & Management (CSD&M 2016), doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-49103-5_14
- [21] G. Génova, J.M. Fuentes, J. Llorens Morillo, O. Hurtado, V. Moreno, "A framework to measure and improve the quality of textual requirements," *Requirements Engineering*, vol. 18(1), pp. 25-41, 2013, doi: 10.1007/s00766-011-0134-z
- [22] G. Giachetti, J.L. de la Vara, B. Marín, "Model-driven gap analysis for the fulfillment of quality standards in software development processes," *Software Quality Journal*, vol. 32(1), pp. 255-282, 2024, doi: 10.1007/s11219-023-09649-x
- [23] J. Guo, J. Cheng, J. Cleland-Huang, "Semantically enhanced software traceability using deep learning techniques," 39th International Conference on Software Engineering (ICSE 2017), doi: 10.1109/ICSE.2017.9
- [24] IEC, IEC 62304 - Medical device software - Software life cycle processes, 2006
- [25] INCOSE, Guide to Writing Requirements, version 4, 2023
- [26] ISO, ISO 14971 - Medical devices - Application of risk management to medical devices, 2019
- [27] ISO: ISO 26262 - Road vehicles - Functional safety, 2018
- [28] itemis, itemis ANALYZE (online) <https://www.itemis.com/en/products/itemis-analyze/> (Accessed Oct 21, 2024)
- [29] F. Klück, Y. Li, M. Nica, J. Tao, F. Wotawa, "Using Ontologies for Test Suites Generation for Automated and Autonomous Driving Functions," 29th IEEE International Symposium on Software Reliability Engineering (ISSRE 2018), doi: 10.1109/ISSREW.2018.00-20
- [30] Y. Li, J. Tao, F. Wotawa, "Ontology-based test generation for automated and autonomous driving functions," *Information and Software Technology*, vol. 117, 106200, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.infsof.2019.106200
- [31] B. Lopez, J.M. Alvarez-Rodríguez, E. Parra, J.L. de la Vara, "Ontology Configuration Management for Knowledge-Centric Systems Engineering in Industry," 50th IEEE/IFIP International Conference on Dependable Systems and Networks (DSN 2020), doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/DSN-S50200.2020.00022>
- [32] J. Llorens, "Knowledge Centric Systems Engineering," South European Systems Engineering Tour (SESE 2014)
- [33] Model Engineering Solutions, MXAM (online) <https://model-engineers.com/en/static-testing-mxam/> (Accessed Oct 21, 2024)
- [34] J.M. Morote, J.L. de la Vara, G. Giachetti, C. Ayora, L. Alonso, "An Industrial Approach for Model-Based Reliability-Oriented System Design," 27th IEEE Pacific Rim International Symposium on Dependable Computing (PRDC 2022), doi: 10.1109/PRDC55274.2022.00036
- [35] D. Mosquera, M. Ruiz, O. Pastor, "Ontology-Based Automatic Reasoning and NLP for Tracing Software Requirements into Models with the OntoTrace Tool," 29th International Working Conference Requirements Engineering: Foundation for Software Quality (REFSQ 2023), doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-29786-1_10
- [36] S. Nair, J.L. de la Vara, M. Sabetzadeh, L. Briand, "An Extended Systematic Literature Review on Provision of Evidence for Safety Certification," *Information and Software Technology*, vol. 56(7), pp. 689-717, 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.infsof.2014.03.001

- [37] E. Parra, C. Dimou, J. Llorens, V. Moreno, A. Fraga, "A methodology for the classification of quality of requirements using machine learning techniques," *Information and Software Technology*, vol. 67, pp. 180-195, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.infsof.2015.07.006
- [38] E. Parra, J.L. de la Vara, L. Alonso, "Analysis of Requirements Quality Evolution," 40th International Conference on Software Engineering (ICSE 2018), doi: 10.1145/3183440.3195095
- [39] E. Parra, L. Alonso, R. Mendieta, J.L. de la Vara, "Advances in Artefact Quality Analysis for Safety-Critical Systems," 30th International Symposium on Software Reliability Engineering (ISSRE 2019), doi: 10.1109/ISSREW.2019.00047
- [40] QRA, Evaluate (online) <https://qracorp.com/evaluate/> (Accessed Oct 21, 2024)
- [41] RGB Medical Devices (online) <https://www.rgb-medical.com/> (Accessed Oct 21, 2024)
- [42] P. Roques, *Systems Architecture Modeling with the Arcadia method*. ISTE Press, 2017, doi: 10.1016/C2016-0-00854-9
- [43] RTCA, DO-178C - Software Considerations in Airborne Systems and Equipment Certification, 2011
- [44] P. Runeson, M. Host, A. Rainer, B. Regnell, *Case Study Research in Software Engineering*. Wiley, 2012, doi: 10.1002/9781118181034
- [45] A.M. Shaaban, C. Schmittner, T. Gruber, A.B. Mohamed, G. Quirchmayr, E. Schikuta, "Ontology-based model for automotive security verification and validation," 21st Int. Conference on Information Integration and Web-based Applications & Services (iiWAS 2019), doi: 10.1145/3366030.3366070
- [46] A. Smrčka, B. Sangchoolie, E. Mingozzi, J.L. de la Vara, M. Farrell, R. Barbosa, C. Baglum, U. Yayan, S. Ergun, A. Kanak, "Towards an extensive set of criteria for safety and cyber-security evaluation of cyber-physical systems," *Open Research Europe*, 2023, doi: 10.12688/openreseurope.16234.1
- [47] The REUSE Company, KM - Knowledge Manager (online) <https://www.reusecompany.com/km-knowledge-manager> (Accessed Oct 21, 2024)
- [48] The REUSE Company, SES Engineering Studio (online) <https://www.reusecompany.com/ses-engineering-studio> (Accessed Oct 21, 2024)
- [49] VALU3S project, D3.1 - V&V methods for SCP evaluation of automated systems. 2020
- [50] VALU3S project, D3.3 - Identified gaps and limitations of the V&V methods listed in D3.1. 2021
- [51] VALU3S project, D3.6 - Final description of methods designed to improve the V&V process. 2022
- [52] VALU3S project, D4.8 - Final Detailed Description of Improved Process Workflows. 2022
- [53] VALU3S project, D4.9 - Final implementation of V&V tools suitable for the improved process workflows. 2022
- [54] VALU3S project, D5.5 - Final Demonstrator Implementation Status Report. 2023
- [55] VALU3S project, Neuromuscular Transmission for muscle relaxation measurements (online) <https://valu3s.eu/healthcare-use-cases/> (Accessed Oct 21, 2024)
- [56] Visure, Requirements Traceability Management Software (online) <https://visuresolutions.com/features/requirements-traceability-management-software/> (Accessed Oct 21, 2024)
- [57] Y. Wang, "Automatic semantic analysis of software requirements through machine learning and ontology approach," *Journal of Shanghai Jiaotong University (Science)*, vol. 21, pp. 692-701, 2016, doi: 10.1007/s12204-016-1783-3
- [58] O. Zaki, M. Dunnigan, V. Robu, D. Flynn, "Reliability and Safety of Autonomous Systems Based on Semantic Modelling for Self-Certification," *Robotics*, vol. 10, 10, 2021, doi: 10.3390/robotics10010010